

INVESTIGATION OF TURBIDITY AND ALKALINITY OF DALSGAR POND WATER

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ABSTRACT

Water analysis reports from a number of laboratories often lack basic description for terminology, potential sources of contaminants or parameters and fail to provide the user an idea of potential concern over the use of the water. In the present study, physiochemical characteristics analysis of sample for pH, Color, Odor, Hardness, Chloride, Alkalinity, TDS etc have been analysed. On comparing the result against drinking water quality standards laid by Indian Council of Medical Research and WHO it is found that some of the water samples are known potable for human being due to high concentration of one or the other parameter. All parameter where cross the permissible limit. The result indicate that Dalsagar pond have contain pollutant and can be only used for domestic and irrigation.

INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the most important and abundant compounds of ecosystem. All living organism on the earth need water for their survival and growth, as of now only earth is the planet having about 70% of water. But due to increasing human population, industrialization use of fertilizers in the agriculture and manmade activity it is highly polluted with different harmful contaminates. Therefore it is necessary that the quality of drinking water should be checked at regular time interval, because due to use of contaminated drinking water human population suffer from varied of water born the biological fully because the chemistry of water reveals much about the metabolism of the ecosystem and explain the general hydro-biological relationship.

There were trend in developing of countries to use sewage effluent as fertilizer has gained much important as it considered a source of organic matter and plant nutrients and serves as good fertilizer. Scientists are mainly interested in general benefit, like increased agriculture, production, low cost water source, effective way of effluent disposal source of nutrients, organic matter etc. but are not well aware of its harmful effect like heavy metal contamination of soil, crops and quality problem related to health. Research has proven that long term use of this notes soil and crops to such an extent that.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Water sample were collected monthly from different sample station of the year Dec 2013 in 1000 ml polythene bottles dalsagar pond (lake) is attached to the seoni city in M.P. The water available to public for his personal requirement is not absolutely pure. Many

cause the physiochemical composition in the water and finally become insoluble for human consumption.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Color of pond water is used to describe the condition of water within the treatment and disposal process. Fresh water is usually a brownish gray tint as they organic material is broken down and the oxygen is depleted the color changes to black [1]. Black waste water is normally anaerobic color intensity increase with an increase in pH for this region reading pH along with color about to be done.

Dalsagar pond is attached to the seoni city (M.P.) the water available to public for his personal requirement is not absolutely pure. the physiochemical composition of the water in the city clearly indicates the need of purification.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:-

Hardness can be quantified by instrumental analysis. The total water hardness is the sum of the molar concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ion mol/L or mmol/l units [2]. Although water hardness usually measures only the total concentration of calcium and magnesium (the two most prevalent divalent metal ions), iron, aluminium, and manganese can also be present at elevated levels in same location. The presence of iron characteristically confers a brownish (rust-like) color to the calcification, instead of white (the color of most of the other compounds).

Water Hardness is often not expressed as a molar concentration, but rather in various units, such as degree of general hardness (dGH), German degrees (dH), parts per million (ppm, mg/l or American degrees), grains per gallon (gpg), English degrees (c, e or clark) or French degrees (FH, F or F lower case f is used to prevent confusion with degrees Fahrenheit). The

table below shows conversion factors between the various units[3-4].

Because it is the precise mixture of minerals dissolved in the water, together with the water pH and temperature, that determine the behavior of the hardness a single, nimble scale does not adequately describe hardness. However the united states. Geological Survey used the following classification into hard and soft water.

Classification	Hardness In mg/l	Hardness In mol/l	Hardness dGH/dH	Hardness in gpg	ppm
Soft	0-60	0-0.60	0-3.37	0-3.50	Less than 60
Moderately Hard	61-120	0.61-1.20	3.38-6.74	3.56-7.01	60-120
Hard	121-180	1.21-1.80	6.75-10.11	7.06-10.51	120-180
Very Hard	>181	>1.81	>10.12	>10.57	>180

Seawater is considered to be very hard due to various dissolved salt. Typically seawater's hardness is in the range of 6630 ppm. In contrast, freshwater has hardness in the range 15-375ppm.

Result

Presence of Mg²⁺ ion 45 mg/l and Ca²⁺ ion 540 mg/l above calculated value of Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions by EDTA complexometric titration method on result clear show that Dalsagar pond water is hard.

ALKALINITY

To determine the constituents and amount of alkalinity of the water.

Requirement:-

- Chemical Reagent:- Standard HCl, water sample.
- Indicator:-Phenolphthalein and methyl orange as an indicator.
- Apparatus:- Burette, pipette, conical flask, measuring flask.

PRINCIPLE: - Alkalinity of water may be attributed due to the presence of the following:-

- Hardness only
- Carbonates

- Bicarbonates
- Hydroxides and Carbonates
- Carbonates and bicarbonates

Any possibility of hydroxides and bicarbonates existing together is ruled out because both combine together to form the respective carbonates.

The extent of alkalinity present in a water sample may be determined by titrating the water sample with a standard acid using phenolphthalein indicator. The disappearance of pink color of the solution indicates the phenolphthalein end point (p). At this stage complete neutralization of hydroxide and conversion of carbonate to bicarbonate takes place.

(equation 1 and 2)

Now add methyl orange indicator and further continue the titration till the color of the solution changes from yellow to pink. It is methyl orange end point (m).

It involves the neutralization of bicarbonates (eq 3), either formed from carbonates in the equation 2 or is present originally in the water sample.

Procedure:-

1.Take out 20 ml of the water sample into a conical flask, add two drops of phenolphthalein indicator and titrate against standard HCl with constant shaking until the pink color just disappears.

Note the titrate value which corresponds to phenolphthalein end point

2.Add 2-3 drops of methyl orange indicator to the same solution and continue titration until a sharp color from yellow to pink takes place.

Note the titrate value as methyl orange end point.

Result: - Alkalinity of water sample due to

- (1) OH⁻ = ppm = 310 mg/l
- (2) CO₃²⁻ = ppm = 4500 mg/l
- (3) HCO₃⁻ = ppm = 840 mg/l

Result and discussion

Author has been workout the physical parameters, total hardness and alkalinity of the Dalsagar pond of the seoni city[5-8]. The total hardness of the pond water is very high because may be calcium carbonate and magnesium carbonate are present in highly amount so this water term to very hard and alkly nature may be pH of the Dalsagar pond water about above 10.5 so this water are harmful to equated life and the result indicate that the this storage water is non populate and can be used for domestic and irrigation.

Analytical data of Dalsagar lake water given in table No.1 result is showed clear that this water is highly turbid grey colour and bad odour.

Water sample was collected and analyzed for physico-chemical parameters by adopting the standard method for examination for water and waste water. The analyses sample attained high values complaint the drinking water. The pH ranged of formed minimum of 6.6 to maximum of 8.4 chlorides from 132.5-820.4 mg/l. Hardness ranged from 74-281mg/l sulphates 0.192-5.12mg/l Nitrates 0.52-1.012. The minimum pH value of 6.3mg/l was found during winter session and maximum of 8.93mg/l in summer. The pH shows general the clean from up steam to down steam CO₂ was found to maximum in summer reaching up to 55.44 mg/l during rainy session. From the data collected it can be concluded that the inverse relationship which is known to exist between pH and CO₂ is not exiting in the present investigation.

Physiochemical characteristics analysis of sample for pH, Color, Odour, Hardness, Chloride, Alkanity, TDS etc have been analysed. On comparing the result against drinking water quality standards laid by Indian council of medical research and WHO it is found that some of the water samples are known potable for human being due to high concentration of one or the other parameter. Study show that changes in physical and chemical parameter like turbidity, TDS, pH and Total Hardness, Chloride, Alkalinity, Sulphate and Nitrates occurs monthly and where analyzed for a periods 6 months. All parameter where cross the permissible limit the result indicate that Dalsagar pond have contain pollutant and can be only used for domestic and irrigation purposes.

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